

JOURNAL OF SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH

Department of Pure and Applied Chemistry

Faculty of Physical Sciences

University of Maiduguri

<http://jsrunimaid.ng>

Research Article

doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.21207479

DETERMINATION OF PESTICIDE RESIDUES (ORGANOPHOSPHORUS AND PYRETHROID) IN FISH SAMPLES FROM RIVER BENUE, VINIKILANG, YOLA, ADAMAWA STATE

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the presence of pesticide residues in the tissues (flesh, liver, bones, and gills) of five commercially available fish species from the Benue River in Viniklang, Adamawa State, Nigeria. The species included *Bagrus bayad*, *Clarias anguillaris*, *Lates niloticus*, *Heterosis niloticus*, and *Auchenoglanis occidentalis*. Pesticides identified in the samples included malathion, fenthion, methyl parathion, disulfotane, fenitrothion, cypermethrin, bifenthrin, permethrin, deltamethrin, and cyphenothrin. Fish samples were processed according to standard procedures, and pesticide concentrations were analyzed using GC-MS. Residues of both pyrethroid and organophosphorus pesticides, such as deltamethrin, cyphenothrin, bifenthrin, permethrin, dichlorvos, and fenitrothion, were detected in all fish samples. Among the species, the highest concentrations were found in the gills of *Auchenoglanis occidentalis*. The detected pesticide levels exceeded the maximum residue limits (MRLs) of 0.05 µg/kg set by the WHO and FAO. The findings underscore the urgent need for education on the risks of improper pesticide use among local farmers and the enforcement of stricter regulations to mitigate potential health risks.

Keyword: Pesticides, Organophosphorus, Pyrethroid, Fish, River

INTRODUCTION

There is growing global concern over the rapid increase in the world's population, along with the urbanization and coastal expansion of many regions. These changes are thought to threaten the productivity and biodiversity of marine food resources due to human-induced pressures. Research suggests that populations with high consumption of marine foods are more likely to accumulate persistent organic pollutants (POPs), such as polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs), as well as certain heavy metals [1,2,3].

The impacts of eating a lot of marine food, including fish products, have been brought to light by people [4]. Additionally, tourism, enjoyment, and human and financial interests all depend on the natural environment. Regardless of whether the pollution is visible (such as plastic and oil pollution) or invisible (such as chemical pollution), the intrinsic value of nature in the same marine and estuarine environments is also increasingly being acknowledged [4,5]. Another significant reason for concern about pollution in marine ecosystems (organisms) is that humans are exposed to these chemicals either directly or indirectly when they consume food from contaminated areas [3,6,7].

Weeds, bug infestations in agricultural areas, and various pests and disease-carrying organisms (including rats, mice, mosquitoes, and ticks) in residences, workplaces, retail establishments, and public spaces are all commonly managed with pesticides. Concerns regarding possible environmental consequences have been raised by pesticide exposure

through a range of pathways, including residues in food and drinking water, because these chemicals lack species-specific modes of action [2,3,5,8].

Although these risks range from short-term (e.g., skin and eye irritation, headaches, dizziness, and nausea) to chronic (e.g., cancer, asthma, and diabetes), they are difficult to pinpoint due to the involvement of multiple factors (e.g., period and level of exposure, type of pesticide (regarding toxicity and persistence), and environmental characteristics of the affected areas). Since no group in the human population is completely immune to pesticides, evaluating public health is challenging because most diseases have multiple causative pathways [7,8].

The high concentrations of pesticides in the water and sediments demonstrate the serious problems with pesticide residues in fish tissues [9]. The liquid and the gills make close contact. The concentration of pesticides in the fish's gills, therefore, is the same as the concentration in the water where they live, while the concentrations in the liver show that the pesticides are stored in the water [10].

Fish samples are among the most crucial markers for determining the degree of pesticide contamination in freshwater systems [11]. The area in fish where pesticides build up is influenced by the intake route. As a result, their potential use as biomonitors is crucial for assessing the bioaccumulation and biomagnification of contaminants within the environment [10].

Vinikilang is a fast-growing village on the slope of Bagale Hill and beside the Benue River. The Benue River flows through Vinikilang in Adamawa State, Nigeria. The River Benue, which extends a considerable distance from Damare, Labong to Vinikilang and Greng, received a wide variety of waste from agricultural land. These waste materials introduce a variety of point-source insecticides into the River Benue. This river is also used for commercial fishing. Most farmers along the banks of the Benue River used pesticides, synthetic chemicals, and fertilizers to control pests on vegetables and boost crop yield. In an attempt to minimize or completely eradicate yield losses and maintain high product quality, these included several extremely persistent organochlorine and organophosphorus pesticides to monitor and manage pests, diseases, weeds, and other plant pathogens. Due to the misuse of these pesticides caused by small and large farmers' ignorance of their effects and usage, trash flows into the Benue River, potentially contaminating it with a variety of pesticides acting as point sources. These contaminants may accumulate in water and sediments, as well as bioaccumulate in fish and other aquatic organisms [5].

Recent years have seen an increase in the use of fish as bioindicators of the integrity of aquatic environmental systems [5,12]. Pesticides should be carefully considered in aquatic toxicology due to their high toxicity and frequent presence, as well as the fact that they bioaccumulate significantly in freshwater fish. Fish have a tendency to accumulate xenobiotic chemicals, especially those that are poorly soluble in water, because they come into such close contact with the medium that contains the xenobiotic chemicals in suspension or solution and because they have to sluice large amounts of water over their gills to extract oxygen from it. Fish populations and those of other animals, including humans, are believed to be declining as a result of fish being killed or injured by The River Benue Area is primarily an agricultural region with high pesticide usage to produce fruits, vegetables, and cereals as well as to prevent vector-borne diseases for public health. Another source of income in the River is fishing. Fish from the River Benue is a major source of protein and the primary source of income for the majority of the local population [13]. Pesticides were used by farmers to boost crop yields, and when it rained, these chemicals and agricultural waste water were dumped into the Benue River. This field of study is a concern for the environment today because of its detrimental effects on both humans and the environment. This trash also has a negative effect on surface water bodies. Locals in the study area rely on the fish caught in the Benue River to meet their protein needs, and the river is the site of many fishing operations. Additionally, the residents get their water from the river. As a result, the possibility of pesticide residues contaminating fish and the aquatic environment is very concerning. Consequently, these fish's different organs may hold an excessive. The purpose of this study was to identify residues of organophosphorus pesticides, such as dichlorvos, diazinon, malathion, fenthion, methyl parathion, disolfotane, and fernerithion, in the flesh, liver, bones, and gills of five commercially important fish species, including *Bagrus bayad*, *Clarias anguillaris*, *Lates niloticus*, *Heterotis niloticus*, and *Auchenoglanis occidentalis*, caught in the River Benue in Vinikilang, Adamawa State, Nigeria, as well as Pyrethroid pesticides, such as cypermethrin, bifenthrin, permethrin, deltamethrin, and cyphenothrin in the flesh, liver, bones, and gills of these five commercially important fish species.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Sample Collection

Fish samples (*Bagrus bayad*, *Clarias anguillaris*, *Heterotis niloticus*, *Lates niloticus*, and *Auchenoglanis occidentalis*) of uniform size were collected in order to prevent any errors resulting from size differences. The fish samples were obtained using gill nets from the River Benue in Vinikilang, Adamawa State, Nigeria. The fish samples were brought to the University of Maiduguri's Fisheries Department so they could be identified. The fish samples were brought to the laboratory that same day, where they were dissected to remove each species' meat, intestine, liver, bone, and gills. They were then stored at 4°C in a refrigerator to be further extracted from and analyzed.

Extraction of Pesticides from Fish Samples

To extract pesticides from fish samples, weigh 20 g of the fish samples into a 150 ml conical flask. Then, add 20 g of anhydrous sodium sulfate and 5 g of sodium hydrogen carbonate, respectively. Once the conical flask is corked, 100 ml of a 1:1 (v/v) ethyl acetate/dichloromethane combination will be added to the 20 g fish samples and properly mixed by shaking. After that, 20 g of sodium hydrogen carbonate and 20 g of anhydrous sodium sulfate were added to the conical flask's contents. After securely corking the conical flask, the mixture was vigorously agitated for ten minutes. The information was left up for three hours. The rotating device was used to evaporate the organic layer after it was decanted into a 200 mL round-bottom flask [1].

Silica Gel Clean-Up of Sample Extracts

A ten gramme (10g) quantity of deactivated silica gel was weighed and then put onto a glass chromatographic column with a 10-mm I.d. After that, three grams of anhydrous sodium sulfate were added. To wet and rinse the column, 10ml of the 1:1 (v/v) ethyl acetate/dichloromethane combination was employed. After transferring the extract residue into the column and rinsing the extract vial three times in two milliliters of ethyl acetate, the vial was introduced to the column. For the second elution, an 80ml quantity of ethyl acetate/dichloromethane was used to elute the column, which was then combined with the first extract. A rotary evaporator set at 40°C will be used to concentrate all of each sample's fractions until they are completely dry. In order to collect each residue for the gas chromatograph, dissolve it in two milliliters of ethyl acetate [1].

De-fattening of the Fish Sample Extracts

The procedure used by [1] was used to de-fatten the sample extracts. To 2 ml of pesticide extracted from the fish samples, 50 ml of a 1:1 (v/v) hexane/acetonitrile solution was put in a 100 mL separatory funnel. While releasing the gas pressure, the separatory funnel was gently shaken for three minutes. To enable the organic solvents to phase separate, the separatory funnel is left in place for 20 minutes. The pesticide-containing acetonitrile fraction was gathered into a 50 ml beaker, and the fat-containing hexane solvent phase was disposed of. Using 25 milliliters of pure hexane, the resultant acetonitrile solvent extract was further cleaned up. Using a rotating evaporator set at 40°C, the acetonitrile fraction was concentrated, and the content.

Determination of Pesticides Residues

Chromatographic separation was performed using a SHIMADZU GC-MS (GC-17A) fitted with a fluorescence detector. Utilizing a 35% diphenyl/65% dimethyl polysiloxane substance in the column allowed for this outcome. The initial temperature of 40°C, 1.5 minutes to reach 150°C, 5.0 minutes to reach 200°C, 7.5 minutes to reach 290°C, and a final hold period of 12 minutes were all programmed into the oven. The column flow rate was kept constant at 1 mL/min. Using the GC-ion trap MS with optional MSN mode, pesticides were detected. Selectivity is improved by the scanning mode offer compared to either full scan or selective ion monitoring (SIM). When a pesticide is eluted in SIM, the ratio of matrix ion intensity to that of pesticide ion intensity increases exponentially as the pesticide's concentration approaches [12].

RESULTS

Concentrations of Organophosphorous Pesticide Residues

The average amounts of dichlorvos, diazinon, chlorpyrifos, and fenitrothion in various *Bagrus bayad* organs from the Benue River near Vinikilang are shown in Figure 1. The organophosphorous pesticide concentrations in *Bagrus bayad* liver ranged from 0.003 to 0.006 mg/kg, 0.003 to 0.008 mg/kg in the gills, 0.002 to 0.004 mg/kg in the flesh, and 0.001 to 0.002 mg/kg in the bones. Additionally, the most common organophosphorous pesticide residue found was diazinon, with values ranging from 0.002 to 0.008 mg/kg, while chlorpyrifos recorded the lowest values, ranging from 0.001 to 0.004 mg/kg. The highest concentration of this pesticide was found in the gills, whereas the lowest value was found in the bones. The organs that are most affected by pesticide bioaccumulation are the liver, meat, bones, and gills. The

concentrations of dichlorvos, diazinon, chlorpyrifos, and fenitrothion in the several *Lates niloticus* organs from the Benue River near Vinikilang are shown in Figure 2. These pesticides ranged in amounts from 0.006 to 0.009 mg/kg in the liver of *Lates niloticus*, 0.004 to 0.006 mg/kg in the gills, 0.003 to 0.004 mg/kg in the flesh, and 0.002 to 0.003 mg/kg in the bones. Gills exhibited the highest quantities of this insecticide, whilst bones showed the lowest levels. The amounts of fenitrothion, dichlorvos, diazinon, and chlorpyrifos in the several organs of *Clarias angularis* from the Benue River near Vinikilang are shown in Figure 3. These pesticide concentrations in *Clarias angularis* liver ranged from 0.003 to 0.004 mg/kg; in gills from 0.003 to 0.006 mg/kg; in meat from 0.001 to 0.002 mg/kg; and in bones from 0.001 to 0.001 mg/kg. Gills contained the largest concentration, whilst bones had the lowest. The amounts of some pesticide residues containing organophosphorus in various *Heterotis niloticus* organs from the Benue River in Vinikilang are displayed in Figure 4. The pesticide's levels in the liver vary from 0.005 to 0.012 mg/kg, the gills from 0.007 to 0.016 mg/kg, the flesh from 0.002 to 0.006 mg/kg, and the bones from 0.001 to 0.002 mg/kg. Gills had the highest concentration, measured at 0.016 mg/kg, whereas bones had the lowest concentration, measured at 0.001 mg/kg. Figure 5 displays the amounts of some organophosphorus pesticide residues in the various *Aucheroglanis occidentalis* organs from the Benue River in Vinikilang. This insecticide has been found at quantities in the liver (0.013–0.016 mg/kg), gills (0.016–0.018 mg/kg), meat (0.003–0.008 mg/kg), and bones (0.002–0.004 mg/kg). Gills had the highest concentration, measured at 0.018 mg/kg, while bones had the lowest, measured at 0.002 mg/kg.

Figure 1: Mean Concentrations of Some Organophosphorus Pesticides in Different Tissues of *Bagrus bayad*

Figure 2: Mean Concentrations of Some Organophosphorus Pesticides in Different Tissues of *Lates niloticus*

Figure 3: Mean Concentrations of Some Organophosphorus Pesticides in Different Tissues *Clarias angularis*

Figure 4: Mean Concentrations of Some Organophosphorus Pesticides in Different Tissues of *Heterotis niloticus*

Figure 5: Mean Concentrations of Some Organophosphorus Pesticides in Different Tissues of *Auchenoglanis occidentalis*

Concentrations of Pyrethroid Pesticide Residues in Fish Samples

The amounts of some pyrethroid pesticide residues found in the liver, gills, meat, and bones of *Bagrus bayad* from the Benue River near Vinikilang are shown in figure 6. The investigated pyrethroid concentrations in *Bagrus bayad*'s liver varied from 1.72 mg/kg to 1.83 mg/kg in its gills. The values for flesh varied between 0.44 and 0.88 mg/kg and 0.23 and 0.63 mg/kg. Of all the pyrethroids under study, the gills had the highest quantities, while the bones had the lowest. The levels of cypermethrin, bifenthrin, permethrin, deltamethrin, and cyphenothrin in the *Lates niloticus* liver, gills, and meat bones from the Benue River near Vinikilang are shown in Figure 7. The amounts of the pyrethroids under study in the liver vary from 0.46 to 1.44 mg/kg, in the gills from 0.53 to 1.56 mg/kg, in the flesh from 0.34 to 0.55 mg/kg, and in the bones from 0.14 to 0.34 mg/kg. The bones display the lowest value of all the pyrethroid concentrations, whereas the gills exhibit the highest amounts. Figure 8 displays the amounts of cypermethrin, bifenthrin, permethrin, deltamethrin, and cyphenothrin in the liver, gills, meat, and bones of *Clarias angularis* from the Benue River near Vinikilang. In the liver of *Clarias angularis*, the examined pyrethroid concentrations varied: 0.61–1.83 mg/kg; 0.68–1.97 mg/kg in the gills; 0.53–1.21 mg/kg in the meat; and 0.32–0.82 mg/kg in the bones. In the liver, gills, meat, and bones of *Heterotis niloticus* from the Benue River in Vinikilang, Figure 9 shows the mean amounts of cypermethrin, bifenthrin, permethrin, deltamethrin, and cyphenothrin. The concentrations in the liver, gills, meat, and bones range from 0.41 to 1.32 mg/kg, 0.48 to 1.43 mg/kg, and 0.31 to 0.42 mg/kg, respectively. as demonstrated in Figure 10 varied between 0.32 and 0.88 mg/kg for *Auchenoglanis occidentalis*; 0.41 and 0.94 mg/kg for gills; 0.24 and 0.23 mg/kg for meat; and 0.08 and 0.13 mg/kg for bones. The comparison of various pyrethroid pesticide concentrations between *Auchenoglanis occidentalis*, *Bagrus bayad*, *Lates niloticus*, *Clarias angularia*, and *Heterotis niloticus* is depicted in Figure 11.

Figure 6: Mean Concentrations of Some Pyrethroid Pesticide Residues in Different Tissues of *Bagrus bayad*

Figure 7: Mean Concentrations of Some Pyrethroid Pesticide Residues in Different Tissues of *Lates niloticus*

Figure 8: Mean Concentrations of Some Pyrethroid Pesticide Residues in Different Tissues of *Clarias*

Figure 9: Mean Concentrations of Some Pyrethroid Pesticide Residues in Different Tissues of *Heterotis niloticus*

Figure 10: Mean Concentrations of Some Pyrethroid Pesticide Residues in Different Tissues of *Aucheroglanis occedentalis*

Figure 11: Comparison in the Concentrations Some Pyrethroid Pesticide Residues between the Five Species of Fish

DISCUSSION

Auchenoglanis occidentalis gills contained the highest concentrations of organophosphorous pesticide residues, whilst *Bagrus bayad* bones contained the lowest concentrations. Pesticides classified as organophosphorous exhibit a greater resistance to microbial breakdown and tend to accumulate in the lipid-rich tissues of aquatic species and the majority of mammals. Their environmental durability, bio-concentration, and bio-magnification along the food chain their most unpleasant traits are directly caused by these features. In contrast to the OPs, dichlorvos, diazinon, chlorpyrifos, and fenitrothion, which microorganisms easily deactivate and breakdown and consequently do accumulate [5,14]. Diazinon and Fenitrothion are the two OPs with the greatest and lowest concentrations, respectively, among those that were determined. In addition to being widely utilized in agriculture, these pesticides are also commonly employed in homes for pest control. The study found that the quantities of organophosphorous pesticide residues, namely diazinon, chlorpyrifos, and fenitrothion, were lower than the maximum residue limits (MRLs) established by Food and Agriculture Organization [2] for diazinon, chlorpyrifos, and fenitrothion, respectively.

The Acceptable Daily Intake levels (ADIs) for fish samples are 0.0002 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ for diazinon, 0.01 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ for chlorpyrifos, and 0.005 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ for fenitrothion, in that order. The present study's results did not surpass the Acceptable Daily Intake thresholds. According to [1,2,15] the maximum residue limits (MRL) are the highest levels of pesticide residue discovered in food ingredients that do not pose a risk to human health. The liver and gills of every fish under study had considerably higher concentrations of these pesticides than any other organ. This is because freshwater fish gills are typically the main pathway for absorbing water pollutants, whereas the liver functions as a storage organ for a wide range of nutrients. High concentrations of this pesticide in the liver and gills may also be the consequence of detoxicating processes, which may start with pesticides left behind in food scraps and sediments in the aquatic environment. Still, the current study suggests that the liver is the organ of choice for pesticide accumulation. This result is consistent with [12], which discovered that the among all the organs, cyphenothrin accumulation was greatest in the gills of *Clarias angularis*, exhibiting a value of 1.97 mg/kg, while *Auchenoglanis occidentalis*' bones displayed the lowest concentration, measuring 0.08 mg/kg. The use of cypermethrin pesticides is essential to contemporary agriculture even if they have negative side effects.

River bodies are one of the main recipients of pesticide residues formed on the field, thus while there is an increase in food supply, issues can develop when a sizable amount of the chemicals are left on the field as residue and tend to impact non-target organisms. On the other hand, Type II pyrethroid exposure causes hyperactivity, incoordination, convulsions, and writhing; these substances also cause stimulus-dependent nerve depolarization and blockage [5,6,7,16,17]. Examples of these pyrethroids are cypermethrin, bifenthrin, permethrin, deltamethrin, and cyphenothrin.

Their environmental durability, bio-concentration, and bio-magnification along the food chain their most unpleasant traits are directly caused by these features. The levels of cypermethrin, bifenthrin, permethrin, deltamethrin, and cyphenothrin found in this investigation were higher than the maximum amounts recommended by the WHO and FAO.

CONCLUSION

Fish samples from all of the study's fish samples tested positive for all of the organophosphorus pesticides (Dichlorvos, Diazinon, Chlorpyrifos, and Fenitrothion) and pyrethroid pesticide residues (Cyphenomethrin, Bifenthrin, Permethrin, Deltamethrin, and Cyphenothrin). The *Auchenogianis occidentalis* gills contained the highest concentrations of these pesticides when compared to other tissues. The results of this investigation showed that the levels of pesticide residue in the fish samples under investigation were below both the acceptable dietary intake (ADI) and the maximum residue limits (MRLs). The maximum residual limits (MRLs) of 0.05µg/kg specified by the WHO and FAO were exceeded by the amounts of cypermethrin, bifenthrin, permethrin, deltamethrin, and cyphenothrin found in this investigation. Because of this, it is necessary to regulate the trade and use of pesticides and to implement suitable punishments in order to prevent farmers in the study area who lack understanding from using these chemicals for pest management. Given that these pesticides were found in the fish samples, it is advised that the appropriate authorities instruct and teach the farmers in the usage of these pesticides. In order to lower the amounts and applications of pesticides in the research environment, there should be constant monitoring of pesticide levels.

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